

Improving resilience to increase nutritional outcomes for women and children in Benin: summary of a field trial

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Background

In Benin, iron deficiency (ID) and anaemia impact 55% of women nationally, which greatly exceeds global standards¹. This high prevalence of ID and anaemia is concerning, as iron-deficient women often experience significant health and socioeconomic burdens, such as impaired cognitive development, reduced work capacity, and adverse pregnancy outcomes². Despite efforts to treat and prevent ID in Benin, women's diets do not meet adequate dietary needs³. This issue is partly due to the lack of suitable and sustainable nutrition interventions available to women in this region⁴. Thus, there is a need to explore alternative solutions suitable to Benin such as the Lucky Iron Fish® (*Fish*). The *Fish* is a re-useable iron fortification cooking tool that has shown to be efficacious at treating anaemia⁵. Coupled with nutrition education, which is known to be a cost-effective solution to address public health problems⁶, the *Fish* may be a more holistic approach to tackle ID and anaemia in Benin.

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Purpose of the study: The purpose of this study was to test the effectiveness of the Lucky Iron Fish® combined with nutrition education delivered through social behaviour change communication methods as a community-based intervention for reducing anaemia among reproductive-age women in Southern Benin.

Objectives and hypothesis:

The objective of this study was to explore the impact of the *Fish* and nutrition education in reducing anaemia and improving knowledge of iron deficiency among women in Benin. We hypothesised that regular use of the *Fish*, coupled with nutrition education, would improve iron status among women in the intervention group compared to the control group, and decrease the prevalence of anaemia at endline of the study.

Methods

Table 1. Study characteristics

Population	Women of reproductive age in Djibja, Benin, with mild or moderate anaemia (n=240)
Intervention	The Lucky Iron Fish (<i>Fish</i>) and nutrition education (six one-hour radio programmes, WhatsApp messages, participation in self-help groups, training sessions) (n=120)
Comparison	Nutrition education, no <i>Fish</i> (n=120)
Outcome	<p>Primary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Iron status (Hb levels) at endline <p>Secondary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prevalence and severity of anaemia at endline Knowledge of anaemia and nutrition at endline Subjective perceptions of changes in health status at endline
Time	Intervention occurred over 6 months Hb was measured at baseline (0 months), midline (3 months), and endline (6 months) Surveys were administered at baseline and endline

Study design

Ethics

This study was approved by The National Ethics Committee for Health Research (CNER) of Benin, and the Ethics Committee of the University of Abomey-Calavi on December 27, 2018. Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Setting

A field trial was conducted in the Djibja region of Benin, West Africa. The intervention was disseminated to 2,375 households. Data were collected from 240 women from different households in the communities in Djibja. Trial activities and data collection were conducted in the communities, adjusted to accommodate COVID-19 pandemic protocols and physical distancing requirements. Households were recruited from villages that were identified as relatively homogeneous in terms of institutional factors (presence of nutrition and food security interventions, proximity or presence of markets) and environmental factors (presence of rivers, drinking water sources), by staff on the ground who discussed with community leaders.

Trial design

Randomised control trial. Participants (n=240) were randomly assigned to intervention (n=120) or control groups (n=120).

Inclusion/exclusion criteria

Eligibility criteria included: women (15 to 49 years old; n=240) living in the Djibja region, with mild (110-119 g/L Hb) to moderate (107-109 g/L Hb) anaemia, free of chronic diseases, and intending to reside in the village in the Djibja region for the duration of the initial trial. Exclusion criteria screened for at enrolment were pregnant women, women with severe anaemia (<107 g/L Hb) or normal Hb levels (>120 g/L), with chronic disease(s), or did not intend to live in the Djibja region for the duration of the trial.

Data collection

Haemoglobin (Hb) levels were measured in the field using a portal haemoglobinometer (HemoCue 201+). Baseline and endline surveys were conducted by the trial staff in the field.

Primary outcome

The primary outcome assessed was change in Hb in the intervention versus the control group.

Key results

Participant characteristics

Two hundred and fifty women were enrolled in the study. Between enrolment and baseline visits, five participants each from the experiment and control groups were lost to follow-up. At baseline, data were collected from 240 women. At endline, data were collected from 152 women due to attrition of 88 women.

Women who received the *Fish* and nutrition education had improvements in haemoglobin levels

The *Fish* and nutrition education had a significant effect on iron status (Hb) among women in the intervention group when compared to the control group. At baseline, there was no significant difference in mean Hb levels between the control (105.6 g/L \pm 15.2) and intervention groups (100.0 g/L \pm 16.3) (Table 1). By endline, there

was a significant increase in mean Hb levels in the intervention group (116.0 ± 16.5 g/L) when compared to the control group (108.6 ± 10.3 g/L) (Table 1). These findings indicate that the *Fish* may be responsible for the increase in mean Hb levels among women in the intervention group.

Table 1. Mean haemoglobin (g/L) levels in intervention versus control groups, at baseline and endline

	Control group (n=120)	Intervention group (n=120)	P value
Baseline	105.6 \pm 15.2	100.0 \pm 16.3	ns
Endline	108.6 \pm 10.3	116.0 \pm 16.5	p<0.05

Data are mean \pm SD (t-test). Statistical significance p<0.05. ns = not significant.

Prevalence of women not anaemic increased by 25% in those who received the *Fish* and nutrition education

At baseline, there was no significant difference between the rates of types of anaemia between the intervention and control groups (6.4% and 7.9% respectively (p>0.05)). By endline of the trial, there was a significant increase in women who were not anaemic in the intervention group when compared to the control group (31.8% and 13.5% respectively (p<0.01)), indicating an increase in women who were no longer anaemic in the intervention group.

Within controls, when comparing levels of anaemia at endline versus baseline, there was a significant increase in women who were not anaemic (Table 2). Within the intervention group, when comparing levels of anaemia at endline versus baseline, there was also a significant increase in women who were not anaemic (Table 2). The proportion of women in the control group who are no longer anaemic increased by 5.6% from 7.9% at baseline to 13.5% at endline. The proportion of women in the intervention group who are no anaemic longer increased by 25.4% from 6.4% at baseline to 31.8% at endline. Collectively these findings suggest that whilst nutrition education helps to reduce the prevalence of anaemia and improve Hb levels, the *Fish* and nutrition education is the most effective.

Table 3. Impact of treatment on levels of anaemia at baseline and endline

	Baseline	Endline	p-value
Control	n=120	n=74	
Not anaemic (>120 g/L)	7.9%	13.5%	p<0.05
Mild (100-119 g/L)	42.8%	41.9%	ns
Moderate (70-99 g/L)	17.7%	12.8%	ns
Severe (<70 g/L)	31.6%	31.8%	ns
Intervention	n=120	n=78	
Not anaemic (>120 g/L)	6.4%	31.8%	p<0.01
Mild (100-119 g/L)	43.9%	24.3%	p<0.05
Moderate (70-99 g/L)	22.7%	17.2%	p<0.05
Severe (<70 g/L)	27.0%	26.7%	ns

Data are % (t-test). Statistical significance p<0.05. ns=not significant.

The *Fish* and nutrition education make women feel healthier and experience fewer symptoms of anaemia
Sixty-four percent of women in the intervention group and 58% of women in the control group reported feeling healthier and experiencing fewer symptoms of iron deficiency and anaemia at endline of the trial.

“I am in good health, I don’t get sick regularly anymore” – participant from control group
“I feel less tired and stronger” – participant from intervention group

Women’s nutritional knowledge and dietary diversity improved

Among the intervention and control groups, eight percent of women at baseline reported knowledge of iron-rich vegetables and by endline, 88% of women were able to identify iron-rich vegetables. At baseline, 57% of women reported making only “traditional” recipes, which were low in iron-rich foods. At endline, women reported an increase in their dietary diversity, with 64% making dishes containing leafy green vegetables more than three times a week to increase their iron intake.

Safety outcomes

No side effects or adverse effects were observed or reported by any of the participants in the trial.

Conclusions

Regular use of the *Fish* coupled with nutrition education can improve iron status, reduce the prevalence of anaemia, and decrease symptoms of iron deficiency among women in Beninese communities.

This study contributes to the field of global health by demonstrating that the *Fish* and nutrition education is an effective community-based intervention package to treat and prevent iron deficiencies in low- and middle- income countries like Benin. Acknowledging the success of the intervention, and significant attrition of participants, the next step in addressing iron deficiency in this region is to understand how to successfully and sustainably scale up implementation of this intervention.

The *Fish* + education
resulted in a
25%
reduction in anaemia

For more information

Contact Lucky Iron Life www.luckyironlife.com

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